

**EPIDEMIOLOGICAL PROFILE OF MORTALITY DUE TO
INTENTIONAL SELF-INJURY IN THE STATE OF SÃO PAULO
BETWEEN 2010 AND 2020**

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Self-inflicted injuries are injuries and poisonings intentionally applied by the person to himself/herself, and suicide attempts. The state of São Paulo ranks 20th in suicide mortality in the country, with 5.4 deaths per 100,000 inhabitants. Therefore, this study aims to analyze the epidemiological profile of mortality from intentional self-harm in the state of São Paulo between the years 2010 to 2020. This is an epidemiological, descriptive, retrospective and cross-sectional study, with a quantitative approach, through data submitted to the Department of Informatics of the Unified Health System - DATASUS and data from the Information System of Notifiable Diseases. The data collected presented information about the macroregion of notification, age group, sex, and color/race. In the state of São Paulo, LAI corresponded to 24,294 between the years 2010 and 2020. The year 2019 presented the highest amount of LAI, corresponding to 2378 cases (9.78%), followed by the year 2020 with 2359 cases (9.71%). Regarding the methodology used for suicide, there is a prevalence of hanging with about 60.2%, occurring a rise of exogenous poisoning with 55.7%. The present study confirms the trends presented in other populations and reinforces the need to adopt interventionist measures in the state of São Paulo, encompassing the identification of potential cases, health education, prevention measures, and encouragement of mental health conservation.

Keywords: Mortality; Epidemiological proliferation; Suicide.

INTRODUCTION

According to the International Statistical Classification of Diseases and Related Health Problems (ICD-10), self-inflicted injuries are injuries and poisoning intentionally applied by the person to himself, and suicide attempts. Intentionally self-inflicted injury (LAI) encompasses suicidal behavior and self-harm, all represented by death at its apex (BAHIA et al., 2017).

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), in 2019, there were more than 97,000 deaths by suicide in the region of the Americas. Brazil is the eighth country in number of suicides among WHO member states, with an average of 24 suicides/day. The states in the southern region of the country have suicide rates above the national average, with emphasis on Rio Grande do Sul and Santa Catarina with the highest suicide rates in the country.

The state of São Paulo ranks 20th in mortality by suicide in the country, with 5.4 deaths per 100,000 inhabitants. underreported cases (BRASIL, 2021).

Therefore, identifying individual risk factors and the main methodologies used for LAI are fundamental in order to reduce suicide rates in the country. Thus, this study aims to analyze

the epidemiological profile of mortality from intentional self-harm in the state of São Paulo between 2010 and 2020. Times New Roman (12) and 1.5 spacing throughout the text.

METHODOLOGY

This is an epidemiological, descriptive, retrospective and cross-sectional study, with a quantitative approach, using data submitted to the Department of Informatics of the Unified Health System – DATASUS and data from the Notifiable Diseases Information System. The information refers to cases of intentionally self-inflicted injuries in the state of São Paulo between 2010 and 2020.

The data collected presented information about the notification macro-region, age group, sex and color/race. The presentation of the results was carried out in the form of tables and graphs, using the Microsoft Excel version 2016 program, a tool for data processing and analysis of simple statistics and construction of graphs. The study site is the state of São Paulo, which is located in the Southeast region of Brazil, and has an estimated population of 46,649,132 people (IBGE, 2021).

The collection of data reported through the DataSUS platform, following the tabs: 1) Health information (TABNET); 2) Vital statistics; 3) Mortality - since 1996 according to ICD-10; 4) Deaths from external causes – São Paulo; 5) Selection of the line “year of death” related to the column Group ICD-10, the other crossings are in table 1; 6) Selection from the range 2010 to 2020.

Chart 1 Intersection for research in the Information System on mortality.

Line	Column
year of death	ICD-10 Group
Sex	ICD-10 Group
ICD-10 Group	age group
Health Macroregion	ICD-10 Group
color/race	ICD-10 Group

RESULTS

Reported cases of intentional self-harm (LAI) in the state of São Paulo corresponded to 24,294 between the years 2010 to 2020. The year 2019 had the highest number of LAI, corresponding to 2378 cases (9.78%), followed by the year of 2020 with 2359 cases (9.71%), as shown in table 1.

Table 1 Deaths from self-harm reported to SIM in the state of São Paulo according to year of death and ICD-10 group.

YEAR OF DEATH	INTENTIONALLY INJURY SELF-INJURY
2010	1964
2011	2047
2012	2097
2013	2205
2014	2232
2015	2300
2016	2199
2017	2306
2018	2207
2019	2378
2020	2359
TOTAL	24,294

Source: Ministry of Health/SVS - Mortality Information System - SIM.

Graph 1 demonstrates a growing pattern of intentionally self-inflicted injuries in the state of São Paulo, with three reductions occurring, one in 2016, representing a reduction of 4.39% of cases, another in 2018, corresponding to a reduction of 4.29%, and a reduction of 0.79% in the year 2020.

Graph 1 Visual demonstration of the number of deaths from intentional self-harm in the state of São Paulo between the years 2010 to 2020.

Regarding sex, the prevalence is in males with 19,157 cases (78.85%). The female gender corresponded to 5133 cases (21.12%), as shown in table 2.

Table 2 Deaths from self-harm reported to SIM in the state of São Paulo according to gender and ICD-10 group.

SEX	INTENTIONALLY INJURY SELF-INJURY
MASCULINE	19,157
FEMININE	5,133
TOTAL	24,294

Source: Ministry of Health/SVS - Mortality Information System - SIM.

In addition, the most affected age group was between 30 and 39 years old, corresponding to 5818 deaths (23.9%), followed by 20 to 29 years old with 5247 deaths (21.59%), 40 to 49 years old with 4666 deaths (19.2%), 50 to 59 years with 3455 deaths (14.22%), 60 to 69 years with 1988 deaths (8.18%), 15 to 19 with 1329 deaths (5.47%), 70 to 79 with 972 deaths (4%), 80 or more with 515 (2.11%), blank or ignored with 91 deaths (0.37%) and 5 to 9 years with 3 deaths (0.01%), as shown in table 3.

Table 3 Deaths from self-harm reported to SIM in the state of São Paulo according to age group and ICD-10 group.

ICD-10 GROUP	BLANK / IGN	5-9	10- 14	15- 19	20- 29	30- 39	40- 49	50- 59	60- 69	70-79	80 OR +	TOTAL
INTENTIONALLY INJURY SELF-INJURY	91	3	210	1329	5247	5818	4666	3455	1988	972	515	24,294
TOTAL	91	3	210	1329	5247	5818	4666	3455	1988	972	515	24,294

Source: Ministry of Health/SVS - Mortality Information System - SIM.

The health macro-region with the highest number of deaths was the 3521 RRAS6, which corresponds to the city of São Paulo, with 4653 deaths (19.21%) due to LAI between the years 2010 to 2020.

Table 4 Deaths from self-inflicted injuries reported to SIM in the state of São Paulo according to health macro-region and ICD-10 group.

HEALTH MACROREGION	INTENTIONALLY INJURY SELF- INJURY
3518 RRAS9	1,424
3519 RRAS8	1,722
3520 RRAS7	1,266
3521 RRAS6	4,653
3522 RRAS5	877
3523 RRAS4	385
3524 RRAS3	322
3525 RRAS2	1,417
3526 RRAS17	1,114
3527 RRAS16	796
3528 RRAS15	2,524
3529 RRAS14	1,029
3530 RRAS13	2,598
3531 RRAS12	1,581
3532 RRAS11	506
3533 RRAS10	927
3534 RRAS1	1,069
TOTAL	24,210

Source: Ministry of Health/SVS - Mortality Information System - SIM

Regarding race/color, there was a higher incidence in white people with 16,694 deaths (68.71%), followed by brown people with 5771 deaths (23.75%), black with 1176 deaths (4.84%), unknown with 394 deaths (1.62%), yellow with 251 deaths (1.03%) and indigenous with 8 deaths (0.03%), as shown in table 5.

Table 5 Deaths from self-inflicted injuries reported to SIM in the state of São Paulo according to health color/race and ICD-10 group.

COLOR/RACE	INTENTIONALLY INJURY SELF-INJURY
WHITE	16,694
BLACK	1,176
YELLOW	251
BROWN	5,771
INDIGENOUS	8
IGNORED	394
TOTAL	24,294

Source: Ministry of Health/SVS - Mortality Information System - SIM

DISCUSSION

In the last 30 years, suicide has become a serious cause of death at all ages in the world. In the year 2015, the number of deaths by suicide worldwide was estimated at 788,000, with a global average of 10.7 per 100,000 population. Suicide ranked second as a cause of death among people aged 15 to 29 worldwide, making it a global public health concern. Suicidal behavior, deliberate self-mutilation and non-suicidal self-mutilation are important antecedents of suicide, which may or may not be present (LIM *et al.* , 2019).

In 2019, 97,339 deaths due to suicide were computed in the Region of the Americas, with suicide attempts estimated to exceed 20 times that number. Between 2010 and 2019, 112,230 deaths by suicide occurred in Brazil, representing an annual increase of 43% in the number of deaths. The analysis of the adjusted mortality rates in the period showed an increased risk of death by suicide in all regions of Brazil (BRASIL, 2021).

In the state of São Paulo, the LAI corresponded to 24,294 between the years 2010 to 2020. The year 2019 had the highest number of LAI, corresponding to 2378 cases (9.78%), followed by the year 2020 with 2359 cases (9, 71%). Regarding the methodology used for suicide, there is a prevalence of hanging with about 60.2%, with an increase in exogenous intoxications with 55.7% (GIANVECCHIO; MELLO JORGE, 2022).

In Brazil, males had a 3.8 times greater risk of death by suicide than females. Among men, the suicide mortality rate in 2019 was 10.7 per 100,000, while among women the suicide mortality rate was 2.9 per 100,000 inhabitants. Comparing the years 2010 and 2019, there was a 29% increase in suicide rates among women, and 26% in rates among men (BRASIL, 2021).

In the state of São Paulo, in terms of gender, prevalence occurs in males with 19,157 cases (78.85%), with females corresponding to 5133 cases (21.12%). Masculinity is associated with low lethality risk behaviors, however suicide attempts most often have high lethality, such

as hanging and the use of firearms. Women, in turn, despite having more attempts, use less lethal methods, such as exogenous drug intoxication (OLIVEIRA *et al.* , 2020).

In addition, males are less likely to seek help for psychological and physical problems, and are more likely to engage in risky behaviors, such as excessive consumption of energy drinks or alcohol, unprotected sex, reckless driving and broad health risk behaviors, including attempts to suicide. LAI are also associated with mental disorders such as substance use disorders, schizophrenia, depression, borderline personality disorder, psychosis, affective disorders, attention deficit hyperactivity disorder and personality disorder (TOFTHAGEN *et al.* , 2021).

In Brazil, the occurrence of self-harm is concentrated in the age group from 20 to 39 years old, with 46.3% of cases, with the age group from 15 to 19 years old in second position, with 23.3% of cases. In the state of São Paulo, the most affected age group was between 30 and 39 years old, corresponding to 5818 deaths (23.9%), followed by 20 to 29 years old with 5247 deaths (21.59%). About 36% of young Brazilians have symptoms of anxiety and depression, which are mainly responsible for the increase in mortality from IAL in this age group from 18 to 24 years old (OLIVEIRA *et al.*, 2020).

In 2019, regarding color/race, Brazil showed a prevalence of suicide mortality in the white population, representing 47.3% of these deaths, followed by the black population with 42.4% of deaths. The indigenous population accounted for 0.5% of deaths by suicide, which despite being a low rate compared to others, has been increasing, especially in the northern region of the country. This reinforces that the transition to adulthood has become a critical period for indigenous youth, especially related to sociocultural transformations resulting from contact with non-indigenous society (SOUSA *et al.*, 2021).

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

Suicide mortality is increasing exponentially worldwide, requiring special attention to the young population, since comprehensive and integrated prevention actions with different sectors of society, such as education, can be carried out in order to prevent suicide . Among the suicide prevention strategies is the need to involve managers and the multidisciplinary health team in planning actions and defining interventions aimed at suicide prevention and intersectoral articulation with the formation of community support networks.

Thus, it is noted that mortality from intentionally self-harm is a serious public health problem, as there is a large increase in the number of cases, representing a sign of psychological

distress in the general population. The present study confirms the trends presented in other populations and reinforces the need to adopt interventionist measures in the state of São Paulo, encompassing the identification of potential cases, health education, prevention measures and encouragement to maintain mental health.

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